

**MAIN GOAL OF THE JUSTICE BODIES IS LEGAL ASSISTANCE
TO POPULATION**

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Annotation. The article contains the reforms in the system of Justice bodies according to the Decree signed by the President No. UP-80 of 24.05.2024 "On Further Increasing Responsibility and Forming a Compact Management System for Justice Bodies and Institutions in the Framework of Administrative Reforms".

Key words: decree, Justice bodies, public service centers, NGO MADAD, legal advice bureaus, "Online-mahalla" platform, Mobile-ID, "Mahalla lawyer", "Legal Advocacy Day".

A half decade ago, to clarify, in 2019 on the portal of discussion of projects of regulatory legal acts, the draft decision of the president of Uzbekistan "On strategic directions of development of Justice bodies and institutions until 2030" was put into public discussion. It was aimed at a consistent increase in the level of legal culture of civil servants.

As a continuation of the reforms, the President signed Decree No. UP-80 of 24.05.2024 "On Further Increasing Responsibility and Forming a Compact Management System for Justice Bodies and Institutions in the Framework of Administrative Reforms".

According to the decree, in order to ensure unconditional compliance with the rights and freedoms of citizens, to further increase the responsibility of Justice bodies and institutions in expanding the scope of state and legal services the following were established as additional areas of activity of the justice authorities:

At first, to identify the legal problems encountered in the daily life of the population, to take practical measures to analyze and eliminate them;

The second direction, development of draft legislative acts aimed at eliminating systemic problems identified in places;

The third direction is connected with establishing and coordinating a system of free primary legal assistance to citizens;

The fourth direction, to provide them with methodological assistance in the formation of uniform law enforcement practices in state bodies and organizations, local state authorities and self-government bodies of citizens.

In cooperation with the NGO "Madad", the Ministry of justice will gradually organize legal advisory bureaus of the NGO "Madad" in public service centers in all districts and cities of the Republic, free legal advice is provided to the population by legal advice bureaus, assistance is provided in the preparation of procedural documents that will be necessary in the pre-trial and judicial resolution of disputes.

The document also provides for an increase in the legal consciousness and legal culture of the population, the transmission of legislative acts to the performers and the effectiveness of work to explain their essence and significance among the population

In this purpose, a project entitled "Mahalla lawyer" is being implemented in citizens' self-governance bodies, under which short-term free training courses are being organised for mahalla chairmen. Every Wednesday in the makhallas will be a "Legal Advocacy Day". On this day, staff of the Ministry of Justice system will conduct: targeted legal outreach activities aimed at the legal solution of problems entered into the "Online-mahalla" platform and identified locally; legal counselling and explanations of the most pressing issues for the population; activities to explain the procedure for granting benefits and material assistance, assigning allowances, protection against unemployment, providing temporary work, and receiving social assistance.

In order to effectively organize the activities of the justice authorities in the regions and further increase the coverage of legal services, the District (City) Justice departments were assigned the following additional tasks:

to conduct "Justice Day" events in neighborhoods every month to review and solve the pressing problems raised by the population in places. In this case, to provide itinerant public services at least twice a month in neighborhoods in remote areas;

preparation of proposals for improving legislation to eliminate legal problems that are identified in the daily life of citizens by walking door-to-door and holding shares of "legal support";

to convey to the "neighborhood seven" the essence and significance of legislative documents in a simple and folk language, as well as to solve the problems of the population with regard to legal issues in their daily lives, which were included by them in the "online neighborhood" platform;

ensuring the provision of free primary legal assistance to the population, first of all, to citizens included in the information system "Iron notebook", "women's notebook", "youth notebook" and "unified register of social protection;

informing young people, women, persons in need of social protection, as well as business entities about the benefits, preferences, subsidies, grants and other types of state support, as well as the procedure for their use, established in the legislative acts;

to provide local state authorities and self-government bodies of citizens with methodological assistance in the formation of uniform law enforcement practices in district (municipal) units of state bodies and organizations.

From 1 July 2024 identification of citizens in the Mobile-ID system is carried out at their request in composite form in the process of issuing ID-card of a foreign passport through the CSU. Electronic copies of archive documents are cancelled from enterprises, institutions and organisations when they are destroyed in accordance with the established procedure. The registration of transactions on the

transfer of non-residential premises to another person is carried out at the personal appearance of the parties to the transaction in the Centralised State Office with the establishment of their identity. The formalised transaction is sent to the cadastre authorities for state registration. By the end of 2024, the method of biometric personal identification (Fase-ID) will be introduced in the provision of public services. At the same time, citizens are not required to provide their identity documents. This project will be held during 6 months as an experiment.

In general, the Ministry of Justice noted that the strategy for the development of the system of Justice bodies and institutions until 2030 will serve as a kind of guideline in the gradual achievement of the goals set in the next decade.

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